

CHIJIKE OKORIE

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CORPORATE GOVERNANCE OF COLLECTING SOCIETIES IN NIGERIA: POWERS OF THE COPYRIGHT SECTOR REGULATOR

* Chijioke Okorie
Lead Consultant, Penguide Advisory

1. Introduction

In 2007, the Nigerian Copyright Commission (NCC), pursuant to its powers under s 39 of the Copyright Act,¹ issued the Copyright (Collective Management Organisation) Regulations 2007 (CMO Regulations) which repealed the Copyright (Collecting Societies) Regulation 1993 (1993 Regulations).² In repealing the 1993 Regulations, the NCC expanded its powers to regulate collective administration of copyright in Nigeria by inter alia making extensive provisions³ relating to the internal mechanisms or corporate governance of collecting societies.⁴ These corporate governance-related provisions discussed later in this paper, marked a turning point in the regulation of collective management of copyright in Nigeria.⁵

The collecting societies regulated by the NCC have “dual personality” and are subject to a dual regulatory framework: they are companies registered under the Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA)⁶ and they are also collecting societies registered pursuant to the CMO Regulations. As companies, they are legal entities with all the rights of natural persons including the right to sue and be sued⁷ and their affairs are governed and managed by their directors and officers under the regulatory framework of the CAMA.⁸ As collecting societies, part of the requirements for the issuance of

¹ Cap C28, Laws of Federation of Nigeria 2004.

² Regulation 23(1) of the CMO Regulations; K Ola *Evolution and future trends of copyright in Nigeria*. (2015) 119-120.

³ See O Ola *Copyright Collective Administration in Nigeria: Lessons for Africa*. (2013) 23-25; IA Olubiyi and KI Adam ‘An examination of the adequacy of the regulation of collecting societies in Nigeria’ (2017) 5 *IPLJ* 93.

⁴ The terms “collecting society” and “collective management organisation” are used in the literature and in different statutes to refer the same entity. This paper prefers and uses the term, “collecting society”.

⁵ Ola 2013 (n3) 51.

⁶ Cap C20 of the Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004 (CAMA).

⁷ See s 38(1) CAMA.

⁸ See s 63 CAMA.

licence to operate their core business of negotiation of licences and collection and distribution of royalties,⁹ include compliance with the directives of the regulatory authority for the copyright sector, the NCC, under the CMO Regulations and adherence to principles of good governance.¹⁰ The legal features and underpinnings of this “dual persona”, although somewhat similar, are distinct enough to warrant separate analyses. Accordingly, it is proposed to address the implications of collecting societies as companies under the CAMA in a later paper.

While there is some literature on the regulation of collecting societies in Nigeria, most have focused on the NCC’s regulation of the activities of collecting societies, particularly in its exercise of its discretionary powers to approve collecting societies¹¹ and others on the effectiveness of the NCC and the CMO Regulations in achieving efficient collective administration of copyright in Nigeria.¹² Little or no attention has been paid to questions relating to the effectiveness of the powers of the NCC under the CMO Regulations in the regulation of the corporate governance of collecting societies.¹³ Therefore, in this article, the overall thrust or concern is the effectiveness of the powers of the NCC under the CMO Regulations, and its specific focus is the effectiveness of those powers in addressing the problems or incidences of poor corporate governance of collecting societies in Nigeria.

Of all the problems or concerns the CMO Regulations were issued to address, the problem of poor corporate governance of collecting societies and the requirements aimed at minimising or addressing them impose “second-generation” requirements on collecting societies in Nigeria. Indeed, the position in Nigeria differs significantly from that of some of its other common law counterparts where there is either a Code of Conduct that applies

⁹ See s 39(8) of the Copyright Act. See also, I Farlam, O Lebogo, N Mhlongo, T Pistorius, J Swanson-Jacobs and M Xulu (Copyright Review Commission) ‘Copyright Review Commission Report 2011’, available at <https://www.gov.za/documents/copyright-review-commission-report-2011> (accessed on 3 March 2018); M Hviid, S Schroff, and J Street ‘Regulating Collective Management Organisations by Competition: An Incomplete Answer to the Licensing Problem?’ (2017) 7 *JIPITEC* 256; Y Jiang ‘Changing tides of collective licensing in China’ (2013) 21 *Mich. St. U. Coll. L. Int’l L. Rev* 729.

¹⁰ Regulation 1(2)(vi) of the CMO Regulations.

¹¹ See JO Odion and DO Oriakhogba ‘Copyright collective management organizations in Nigeria: resolving the locus standi conundrum’ (2015) 10(7) *Journal of Intellectual Property Law & Practice* 518; V Nzomo ‘Collective Management of Copyright and Related Rights in Kenya: Towards an Effective Legal Framework for Regulation of Collecting Societies’, available at <<https://ssrn.com/abstract=2929231>> (accessed 3 March 2018).

¹² See Ola 2013 (n3).

¹³ See Nzomo (n11) at 77.

to collecting societies specifically or a Code of Corporate Governance that has been applied to collecting societies. For instance, in both the United Kingdom¹⁴ (UK) and Australia,¹⁵ there is a Code of Conduct adopted by or applicable to collecting societies while in South Africa; the King III Report¹⁶ on corporate governance has been applied to collecting societies.¹⁷ In Nigeria, while there are several codes of corporate governance proposed to guide Nigerian companies with regard to acceptable corporate governance practices generally,¹⁸ there is presently no code of conduct or code of corporate governance specifically applicable to collecting societies.

The regulation of the corporate governance of collecting societies is particularly contextual and often entails issuing directives depending on the circumstances of each collecting society and the conduct of the officers and directors of the relevant collecting society involved in the management of its affairs.¹⁹ Further, issues of corporate governance affect the very existence of the collecting societies themselves and incidences of poor corporate governance can lead to the “death” of the affected collecting society.²⁰ The winding up of the affairs of the South African Recording Rights Association Limited (SARRAL) over corporate governance failures is a case in point.²¹ Accordingly, given the extensive powers of the NCC with respect to the corporate governance of collecting societies in Nigeria, this paper questions whether the powers of the NCC are effective in

¹⁴ See for example, PRS for Music ‘PRS for Music Code of Conduct’, available at <<https://www.prsformusic.com/-/media/files/prs-for-music/corporate/governance/code-of-conduct/prs-for-music-code-of-conduct.pdf>> (viewed 20 August 2018), British Copyright Council ‘Principles for Collective Management Organisations’ Codes of Conduct’, available at http://www.britishcopyright.org/files/2614/1312/8143/BCCPGP_Policy_Framework_250512.pdf (viewed 20 August 2018).

¹⁵ Australian Competition and Consumer Commission ‘Code of Conduct for Collecting Societies’, available at https://www.accc.gov.au/system/files/public-registers/documents/D09_171037.pdf (viewed 20 August 2018).

¹⁶ Institute of Directors Southern Africa ‘King Report on Governance for South Africa 2009’, available at https://cdn.ymaws.com/www.iodsa.co.za/resource/resmgr/king_iii/King_Report_on_Governance_fo.pdf (viewed 20 August 2018).

¹⁷ See *Copyright Review Commission Report 2011* (n9).

¹⁸ For example, Securities and Exchange Commission ‘Code of Corporate Governance for All Public Companies’, available at sec.gov.ng/code-of-corporate-governance-for-public-companies_may-12-2014/ (viewed 15 March 2018).

¹⁹ See MA Jaimes-Valdez, CA Jacobo-Hernandez, S Ochoa-Jimenez ‘Corporate Governance: International Context and Trends from 2005 to 2015’ (2017) 12(3) *International Journal of Business and Management* 159.

²⁰ See *Copyright Review Commission Report 2011* (n9) 46.

²¹ See the decision of the South Gauteng High Court in Johannesburg in *Shapiro v South African Recording Rights Association Limited* judgment delivered on 6 November 2009.

addressing corporate governance issues as the CMO Regulations seek to do.

Given the thrust of this paper on the effectiveness of the regulatory powers of the NCC in the corporate governance of collecting societies, section 2 briefly discusses the concept of effectiveness in order to provide a conceptual framework for the discourse. Section 3 provides a snapshot of the business of collecting societies in Nigeria and the rationale for regulating the corporate governance of collecting societies. This is essential as it offers useful insights into the factors that might influence the effectiveness of the powers of the NCC as the regulatory authority in corporate governance of collecting societies in Nigeria. Section 4 answers the core question of this paper: are the powers of the NCC under the CMO Regulations effective in facilitating good corporate governance practices or addressing problems of poor corporate governance of collecting societies, and if not why? Section 4 answers this question by first identifying the nature and scope of the obligations placed on collecting societies with respect to their corporate governance. Using the effectiveness parameters set out in section 2 of this paper, section 4 evaluates the effectiveness of the NCC's powers by considering what lines of action are open to the NCC in the event of non-compliance with the requirements of good corporate governance. Section 5 makes recommendations for improving the effectiveness of the NCC in regulating the corporate governance of collecting societies in Nigeria. Both in considering the question of the effectiveness of the NCC in regulating the corporate governance of collecting societies and in recommending ways to improve effectiveness, this paper draws on examples from Australia. Australia has made significant progress in the regulation of the corporate governance of collecting societies. It can therefore provide lessons for the future of the regulation of the corporate governance of collecting societies in Nigeria. Compliance with its code of conduct for collecting societies is reviewed annually for each signatory and the code itself is reviewed triennially to ensure that it continues to facilitate best practices in the corporate governance of collecting societies. Section 6 concludes.

2. What is effectiveness?

Effectiveness can mean different things depending on the contexts. Young and Levy characterise effectiveness into different contexts: legal, economic, normative, problem

solving, and political.²² Legal effectiveness concentrates on compliance and asks whether or not the targeted actors in a given legal regime act in accordance with the rules specified in the regime.²³ However, while this approach to measuring effectiveness is relatively easier, it may result in a purely formal analysis, which would not consider the substance of the legal regime itself. Normative effectiveness refers to whether or not a regime succeeds in achieving specific values, such as participation and provision of a level playing field for all its targeted actors. Economic effectiveness on the other hand, involves a consideration of the economic costs of addressing the problems a regime set out to resolve.²⁴ Political effectiveness refers to the effectiveness of a regime in changing the conduct of actors in favour of better management of the subject(s) regulated by the regime. Based on this parameter, Young suggests that a regime could be "politically" effective without being legally effective.²⁵ Effectiveness in problem solving is the most innate: whether or not a regime solves the problem that the regime is supposed to combat or to help resolve. Assessing the effectiveness of a regime from a problem-solving perspective involves the question of whether a regime is able to achieve its key objectives or examines the extent to which a given regime eradicates or alleviates the problems that prompted it.²⁶ This evaluation of whether a regime solves the problems it set out to address is also an approach adopted by the courts in Nigeria interpreting statutory provisions. One of the rules of interpretation – the mischief rule – interprets statutory provisions by giving them a meaning that ensures it addresses the mischief or the problems which it set out to achieve in the first place.²⁷

Admittedly, there are some ambiguities in applying any of these classifications. However, the classifications are useful as a starting point in the analysis of any regime. The questions posed in this paper could be classified as problem-solving approaches to

²² OR Young and MA Levy *The Effectiveness of International Environmental Regimes* in OR Young (ed) *The Effectiveness of International Environmental Regimes: Causal Connections and Behavioral Mechanisms* (1999) 4-5.

²³ WB Chambers 'Towards an improved understanding of legal effectiveness of international environmental treaties' (2003) 16 *Geo. Int'l Env'tl. L. Rev.* 518; Young and Levy (n22).

²⁴ Young and Levy (n22).

²⁵ OR Young (ed) *The effectiveness of international environmental regimes: Existing knowledge, cutting-edge themes, and research strategies*. In *Advances in International Environmental Politics*. (2014) 278.

²⁶ See also, EB Weiss and HK Jacobsen (eds) *Engaging Countries: Strengthening Compliance with International Accords* (1998).

²⁷ See the decision of the Nigerian Supreme Court in *Ifezue v. Mbadugha & Anor* (1984) N.S.C.C vol.15, 314.

the question of effectiveness. The analysis of the effectiveness of the powers of the NCC under the CMO Regulations in facilitating best corporate governance practices and preventing or sanctioning poor corporate governance of collecting societies is a problem-solving approach. This idea of problem-solving "effectiveness" moves attention away from formalism and directs it to substance. The enquiry is not directed to the formal language of a regime, but rather to whether or not it does any thing useful for the corporate governance of collecting societies in Nigeria.

It is important to measure the effectiveness of a regime by examining the regulatory authority within the regime itself and answering the question of what makes its powers effective or ineffective. In its work on corporate governance of collecting societies, the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) defined effective regulation to include the availability of effective, proportionate and dissuasive sanctions in the event of non-compliance with regulatory directives.²⁸ In particular, the OECD showed that the availability of resources to enforce compliance with regulatory directives has significant influence in facilitating good corporate governance in collecting societies. This gives an insight into analyzing the effectiveness of the powers of the regulatory authority in facilitating good corporate governance in collecting societies regulation, and has been applied in this paper. Recently, the NCC suspended the licence of one of Nigeria's foremost collecting societies, the Collecting Society of Nigeria (COSON) for its refusal to comply with corporate governance directives issued by the NCC.²⁹ Despite the suspension, COSON has continued operations and has reportedly challenged its suspension in court.³⁰ Since this would be the first time that the actual corporate governance of a Nigerian collecting society has attracted the attention of the regulatory authority, COSON's case and the exercise of powers by the NCC offers a quasi-experiment in examining its (the NCC's) effectiveness in addressing corporate governance matters.

²⁸ OECD 'Methodology for assessing the implementation of the OECD principles of corporate governance', available at <https://www.oecd.org/corporate/ca/37776417.pdf> (accessed on 2 April 2018).

²⁹ I Egbunike 'NCC Suspends Operating License of Copyright Society of Nigeria (COSON)', available at <http://www.copyright.gov.ng/index.php/news-events/item/432-ncc-suspends-operating-license-of-copyright-society-of-nigeria-coson> (viewed 16 May 2018).

³⁰ See O Ovie 'Looming Revocation of COSON License: Industry Heavyweights Demand Affirmative Action', available at <https://notjustok.com/article/looming-revocation-of-coson-license-industry-heavyweights-demand-affirmative-action/> (viewed 12 June 2018).

3. The business of and the rationale for regulating the corporate governance of collecting societies

In order to contextualise the question of the effectiveness of the powers of the NCC in facilitating good corporate governance in collecting societies, it is important to understand the nature of the business of collecting societies.

3.1 The business of collecting societies

Section 39(8) of the Copyright Act defines a collecting society to mean “an association of copyright owners which has as its principal objectives the negotiating and granting of licenses, collecting and distributing of royalties in respect of copyright works”. Also, by virtue of s 39(2)(b) of the Copyright Act, an approved collecting society must have as its main objects, “the general duty of negotiating and granting copyright licenses and collecting royalties on behalf of copyright owners and distributing same to them”. Furthermore, s 17 of the Copyright Act provides that “any person carrying on the business of negotiating and granting of licences and collecting and distributing royalties in respect of copyright works or representing more than fifty owners of copyright in any category of works” requires approval to “operate as a collecting society”. A combined reading of these provisions shows that the primary duties of a collecting society are: negotiating and granting licenses to users of copyright works; collecting royalties from users of copyright works and distributing the royalties to copyright owners. While collecting societies engage in other corporate functions outside the traditional functions of licence negotiation and grant, royalty collection and distribution and these functions may differ across jurisdictions, the core functions are usually the same in many jurisdictions.³¹ To undertake these core traditional functions of negotiating and granting licences, a collecting society needs the mandate of copyright owners. It also needs to be able to enforce such mandate by collecting royalties from users for their uses of copyright works covered by the collecting society’s mandate. Finally, a collecting society must distribute the royalties collected to the owners of the relevant copyright works.³²

The mandate of copyright owners is secured by a deed of assignment or a membership agreement between the collecting society and each copyright owner

³¹ C Handke and R Towse (2007) ‘Economics of Copyright Collecting Societies’ 38 *International Review of Intellectual Property and Competition Law* 937-938.

³² *Ibid.*

stipulating the rights owned and now assigned to the collecting society, the territories covered by the assignment as well as other rights covered by the assignment.³³ Because of their centrality, collecting societies offer authors and copyright owners a stronger bargaining power in dealing with large-sized firms that use copyright works.³⁴ By aggregating a critical mass of copyright owners and copyright works, collecting societies give authors the benefit of a single cohesive unit that can ensure fairer contracting terms for the exploitation of their work.³⁵ By virtue of the deed of assignment executed by its members, a collecting society becomes an assignee or exclusive licensee of copyright. As such assignee or exclusive licensee of copyright, a collecting society does not lose its proprietary interests in the copyright works regardless of the approval or non-approval of the regulatory authority.³⁶

In the case of structures to enforce the deed of assignment, collecting societies fix tariffs and terms for blanket licenses issued to users to pay royalties for use of the applicable copyright works. By virtue of its status as assignee or exclusive licensee of copyright, a collecting society acts on behalf of its members in negotiating and granting licences to users of copyright works. On the basis of such licensing agreements, users of copyright works pay the applicable royalties to the copyright owners through the relevant collecting society.³⁷ Where users fail to pay the agreed or applicable royalties, collecting societies may enforce their mandate in court and sue the relevant users for copyright infringement.³⁸ It is to be noted here that the suit to be initiated by the collecting society may be for copyright infringement or for breach of contract depending on whether the collecting society has obtained the approval of the regulatory authority to operate as a collecting society.³⁹

Another structure for the enforcement of the mandate of copyright owners is the reciprocal representation agreement, which is “any agreement between foreign collecting

³³ See L Guibault and S Schroff ‘Extended Collective Licensing for the Use of Out-of-Commerce Works in Europe: A Matter of Legitimacy Vis-à-Vis Rights Holders’ *IIC-International Review of Intellectual Property and Competition Law* 1-2.

³⁴ *Ibid* at 2.

³⁵ Olubiyi and Adam (n3) 93.

³⁶ N Bortloff ‘Collective management of rights in musical, literary and dramatic works in Europe’ (1997) 6 *Ger. Am. LJ* 67.

³⁷ Guibault and Schroff (n33) 2-3.

³⁸ Odion and Oriakhogba (n11) 518.

³⁹ *Ibid* at 524.

societies and indigenous collective management society whereby one collective management organisation grants to the other the right to manage its repertoire in the territory of the other”.⁴⁰ Under such arrangements, collecting societies have been able to administer the copyright of their members in many foreign jurisdictions through the resident collecting society and thus, avoid the prohibitive costs and technical challenges of doing so directly.⁴¹ For instance, Nigerian collecting societies such as COSON and MCSN have respective reciprocal management agreements with collecting societies in other countries and have obtained membership of the International Confederation of Authors and Composers Societies (CISAC). CISAC is a not-for-profit organisation that provides a network of several author societies in the world. CISAC has established and operates many tools that enable collecting societies represent authors across multiple jurisdictions and track usage and royalty flow for authors anywhere in the world. For instance, CISAC operates qualifiers and identifiers such as International Standard Musical Work Code⁴² (ISWC) and the Interested Parties Information⁴³ system (IPI), which inter alia forms the basis for determining ownership of musical works and by extension, accrued royalties and members entitled to such royalties. As a member of the CISAC, a collecting society can enforce its mandate in any jurisdiction covered by CISAC’s members and has access to all of the CISAC’s tools such as the ISWC and the IPI. CISAC established a set of professional rules relating to corporate governance, which are subject to relevant laws and regulations.⁴⁴ However, while CISAC rules encourage members to be accredited or licensed by the relevant national regulatory authority for collecting societies prior to operating as collecting societies, such requirement is not a condition for membership.⁴⁵ For instance, MCSN became a member of CISAC even prior to obtaining the approval of the NCC to operate as a collecting society in Nigeria. By

⁴⁰ See Regulation 22(1) of the CMO Regulations.

⁴¹ See Olubiyi and Adam (n3) 92; G Mazziotti ‘New licensing models for online music services in the European Union: from collective to customized management’ (2010) 34 *Colum. JL & Arts* 762-763.

⁴² See J Bing ‘The contribution of technology to the identification of rights, especially in sound and audio-visual works: An overview’ (1996) 4(3) *International Journal of Law and Information Technology* 234-254. See also <http://www.iswc.org/en/faq.html>.

⁴³ See Bing (n42) 237; A Powell ‘Unique identifiers in a Digital World’ (1997) 8 *Ariadne* 1; <https://www.ipisystem.org>.

⁴⁴ See CISAC ‘Professional rules for music societies’, available at <http://www.cisac.org/What-We-Do/Governance/Professional-Rules> (viewed on 27 August 2018).

⁴⁵ *Ibid* at para 20. See also, CISAC ‘Statutes’, available at <http://www.cisac.org/What-We-Do/Governance/Statutes> (viewed on 27 August 2018).

virtue of its membership of CISAC, a collecting society (such as MCSN) is able to offer its members the benefit of CISAC's standard tools and provide access to information regarding the royalty chain and remuneration.⁴⁶

In essence, where a collecting society is no longer able to negotiate and grant licences and/or collect and distribute royalties, its business is significantly affected. As argued in subsequent sections of this paper, where the exercise of the powers of the regulatory authority can significantly affect the ability of any collecting society to carry out this core business, the chances of the society's compliance with directives from the regulatory authority are much higher.⁴⁷

3.1. Rationale for the regulation of the corporate governance of collecting societies

The role of collecting societies is integral to the copyright economy. They provide a database of information on copyright ownership, set royalty rates for copyright licences, receive royalties on behalf of copyright owners, distribute royalties to copyright owners, and provide a variety of copyright education and management for the economy at large.⁴⁸ The directors or management of collecting societies owe a fiduciary duty to their members, on the basis of their handling finances on their behalf.⁴⁹ The continued existence of the collecting society as a company lies in the proper governance of its affairs by its officers.⁵⁰ Regulatory scrutiny of the corporate governance of collecting societies is therefore an important concept. Otherwise, because directors of a collecting society are agents of the collecting society itself and agents of the members,⁵¹ where they mismanage the affairs of the collecting society, it may ultimately lead to the death of the collecting society as a legal person and jeopardise the interests of copyright owners.⁵² Indeed, if the finances of a collecting society are not properly managed and applied, it is unlikely that the collecting society would continue to operate as a going concern.⁵³ Where

⁴⁶ Ibid. See also Bing (n42).

⁴⁷ See JW Williams 'Out of place and out of line: Positioning the police in the regulation of financial markets' 30(3) *Law & Policy* 306-335. Also OECD (n28).

⁴⁸ See Handke and Towse (n31) 937-938.

⁴⁹ See Olubiyi and Adam (n3) 107; Section 279 of CAMA; *Astra Industries v NBCI* [1998] 3 SC 98; R Marens and A Wicks 'Getting real: Stakeholder theory, managerial practice, and the general irrelevance of fiduciary duties owed to shareholders' (1999) 9(2) *Business Ethics Quarterly* 273-293.

⁵⁰ See A Loos (ed) *Directors' Liability - A Worldwide Review* 3 ed (2016) 373.

⁵¹ Farlam (n3).

⁵² See *Shapiro v South African Recording Rights* supra para 20 at 33.

⁵³ Ibid.

there is no limit to the exercise of powers by management or where there are no regulatory sanctions or provisions to ensure that actions of management are necessary or can be reasonably justified, the collecting society may suffer corporate death as a direct consequence of bad corporate governance.⁵⁴ A case in point is that of SARRAL, which became insolvent and was subsequently wound up because of the poor corporate governance of the company by its directors.

As noted in the previous section, collecting societies perform other functions outside the traditional functions of negotiation and grant of licences and collection and distribution of royalties.⁵⁵ The funds used to execute these “non-traditional” functions are usually from a certain percentage of royalties received and which the collecting societies are permitted to retain. Thus, there is a growing concern that the conduct of the management of collecting societies may compromise the legitimate business interests of copyright owners who assigned their rights to such collecting societies, such as unprejudiced treatment, transparency and due process.⁵⁶ It is submitted that the convergence of these traditional and socio-cultural functions by collecting societies, and the large volume of funds (copyright owners’ royalties) controlled by collecting societies, necessitates a critical examination of their corporate governance structures and regulatory scrutiny of the management of such structures.⁵⁷ The major concern in this instance is that opportunity exists for some officers of a collecting society to retain a higher percentage outside the statutory stipulated percentage and divert some of these funds in the guise of performing socio-cultural functions.⁵⁸ In the absence of regulation of the corporate governance of such collecting society, the relevant officers may have no compulsion to provide accurate and complete information or to act in a transparent manner. The basic idea is that in the absence of rules for corporate governance, managers have an information advantage and that this may give them the opportunity to take actions in their selfish interests.⁵⁹ Recent years have seen a growing incidence of directors of collecting societies applying the funds belonging to the collecting societies to

⁵⁴ See SEC (n18).

⁵⁵ See A Harcourt ‘The unlawful deduction levied upon UK composers’ performing rights income’ (1996) 64 *Copyright World* 15.

⁵⁶ *Ibid.*

⁵⁷ See Harcourt (n55) 15. See also, Olubiyi and Adam (n3) 93.

⁵⁸ F Allen and D Gale (ed) *Comparing financial systems* (2000) 93 – 97.

⁵⁹ *Ibid.*

projects and schemes without approval from members.⁶⁰ For instance, the directors of South African Music Rights Organisation (SAMRO) were alleged to have invested the members' funds in a Dubai "ponzi" scheme without members' approval and lost over R40 million.⁶¹ The directors of Music Copyright Society of Kenya were alleged to have embezzled members' royalties.⁶² In the case of the COSON, the NCC has indicated that it had received a petition regarding the absence of sufficient explanation as to the conduct of some members of COSON's Board in applying members' funds towards other objectives outside collection and distribution of royalties, and the process of removal and reinstatement of Board members without due process.⁶³

It is argued that corporate governance principles, or the framework of rules and practices by which directors ensures accountability, fairness, and transparency in a company's relationship with its stakeholders, is what determines the viability of a collecting society as a corporate entity. Infighting between members of the governing board of a collecting society, mismanagement of its finances, unethical conduct, detrimental conflict of interests - may lead to manipulation and abuse of power, create new barriers to open competition and market innovation, and challenge the copyright system.⁶⁴ Through the prism of corporate governance rules, the general public can scrutinise the manner in which collecting societies are operated and shape their actions accordingly. Particularly, copyright owners may choose to avoid the services of collecting societies that appear to abuse their power against the economic and creative interests of copyright owners.

The integral role that collecting societies play in the copyright economy is

⁶⁰ For example, see PRS 'Public Hearing on Governance and Transparency of Collective Management of Rights - Relations between societies' available at http://ec.europa.eu/internal_market/copyright/docs/management/hearing20100423/panel_2_prs%20for%20music_en.pdf (viewed on 17 June 2018).

⁶¹ Z Fenner 'Musicians of SAMRO lose R40 million due to bad investment decision', available at <https://idmmag.com/news/musicians-of-samro-lose-r40-million-due-to-bad-investment-decision/> (viewed 10 May 2018).

⁶² T Matiko 'Music Copyright Society of Kenya now banned from collecting music royalties', available at <https://nairobi.news.nation.co.ke/chillax/music-copyright-society-of-kenya/> (viewed 10 June 2018).

⁶³ A Ezekude 'Text of press briefing by the Director General, Nigerian Copyright Commission, Mr. Afam Ezekude, on the dispute in the governing board of Copyright Society of Nigeria Ltd/Gte (COSON)', available at <http://www.copyright.gov.ng/index.php/news-events/item/427-text-of-press-briefing-by-the-director-general-nigerian-copyright-commission-mr-afam-ezekude-on-the-dispute-in-the-governing-board-of-copyright-society-of-nigeria-ltd-gte-coson> (viewed on 18 June 2018).

⁶⁴ S Bhagat, B Bolton and R Romano 'The promise and peril of corporate governance indices' (2008) 108 *Colum L Rev* 1809-1811.

demonstrated by the almost universal practice of states in regulating collecting societies and providing, in many cases, an operating licence scheme to protect copyright owners when collecting societies engage in unethical conduct.⁶⁵ The regulation of collecting societies in Nigeria requires the issuance of a licence to operate, the application for licence renewal upon expiration and provision for revocation of licences in deserving cases.⁶⁶ It is imperative that regulatory authorities ensure that collecting societies have strong governance structures, particularly in the light of the amount of information and monies they control.⁶⁷ Regulatory scrutiny of the corporate governance of collecting societies is important in the interests of the corporate existence and viability of collecting societies; the interests of copyright owners and in the preservation of a sound copyright system.

4. Are sector regulatory powers in corporate governance issues effective in facilitating good corporate governance practices?

The core question, which this paper seeks to address, is whether the powers of the NCC under the CMO Regulations achieve what it is intended to achieve in regulating corporate governance - that is, facilitate good corporate governance practices in collecting society. This question may be simple, but it is not so straightforward to answer. It depends on the analyst's judgment as to what counts as a "satisfactory" outcome.⁶⁸ As stated in section 2 of this paper, effective regulation involves the availability of effective, proportionate and dissuasive sanctions in the event of non-compliance with regulatory directives.⁶⁹ Here, there is an assessment of the extent of compellability of the powers of the NCC in sanctioning non-compliance with its directives and the CMO Regulations as it pertains to the corporate governance of collecting societies. Put differently, what are the consequences for non-compliance with good corporate governance principles and directives related to them and how dissuasive are those consequences for collecting societies? Where there are prohibitive or dissuasive sanctions for non-compliance, the exercise of the powers of the regulatory authority will be considered effective, and as such, a satisfactory outcome.

⁶⁵ Olubiyi and Adam (n3) 94-96.

⁶⁶ See Regulations 1 and 3 of the CMO Regulations.

⁶⁷ Olubiyi and Adam (n3) 107.

⁶⁸ K Iida 'Is WTO Dispute Settlement Effective?' (2004) 10(2) *Global Governance* 211.

⁶⁹ *Ibid.*

The corporate governance framework encompasses statutes, regulation, and standards including case law, codes and principles and business practices. In Nigeria, the corporate governance framework for collecting societies is established through a combination of the Copyright Act⁷⁰ and the CMO Regulations.⁷¹ While the provisions of the CAMA also apply to collecting societies in Nigeria, such is outside the scope of this paper. The corporate governance provisions under the CMO Regulations are split between those requirements that must be satisfied prior to approval and those required in the course of running/operating the collecting society as a going concern.

By virtue of s 39(2)(a) of the Copyright Act, a collecting society must be a company limited by guarantee and as such, not a for-profit company. The CMO Regulations require every collecting society to have a General Assembly of all its members and a Governing Board, which would be responsible for taking decisions on behalf of the society and running the affairs of the society.⁷² The Governing Board exerts corporate governance over all employees of the collecting society, including the General Manager, and can fire any of them at any time. The objectives for which such collecting society was set up are to be stated in its memorandum and articles of association and its main objectives must include the negotiation and granting of licences, the collection and distribution of royalties.⁷³

The Governing Board of each collecting society is to be comprised of all the Directors of the society, the General Manager of the society and a representative of the NCC who has no voting rights and is involved as an observer.⁷⁴ While the Directors of the society are required to be members of the collecting society, the CMO Regulations stipulate that the General Manager should not be a member of the collecting society.⁷⁵ The Governing Board also keeps the books of account of the society and each member of the Governing Board is entitled to access the books at any time.⁷⁶

When it comes to the operation of the affairs of collecting societies, it is effectively the officers and directors of the collecting society who must adhere to the

⁷⁰ See s 39(1) Copyright Act.

⁷¹ For example, see Regulation 2 of the CMO Regulations.

⁷² See Regulation 2(3)(ii) and (iv) of the CMO Regulations. See also, ss. 35 and 244(1) of the CAMA.

⁷³ For example, see paragraphs 3(a)-(m) of the memorandum of association of COSON

⁷⁴ See Regulation 2(3) of the CMO Regulations.

⁷⁵ See Regulation 2(3)(iii) of the CMO Regulations.

⁷⁶ See Regulation 8 of the CMO Regulations.

provisions set by the governing law legitimising their existence.⁷⁷ When performing its functions as a company meant to serve the interests of its members and the public at large, the officers and members of the Governing Board of a collecting society effectively embody the collecting society itself.⁷⁸ The primary responsibility for ensuring good corporate governance in companies lies with the Board. The requirement of having a Governing Board and a corporate governance structure is in place to ensure that collecting societies carry on their business in accordance with their articles and memorandum of association and in conformity with relevant statutes.⁷⁹ Whether collecting societies are effective or inefficient and whether they abuse their monopoly to the detriment of copyright owners and users is a function of their Governing Board.

The General Assembly and the Governing Board and the rules set out in the collecting society's memorandum and articles of association provide the corporate governance structure of each collecting society. Compliance with this structure is required to apply to the NCC for approval to operate as a collecting society.⁸⁰ In the absence of these structures, the NCC will not grant the requisite approval to such prospective collecting society. The NCC has approved the following organisations to operate as collecting societies in Nigeria: COSON which comprises of copyright owners of musical works and sound recordings, Reprographic Rights Organisation of Nigeria (REPRONIG) comprising of copyright owners of literary works, and the Audio Visual Society of Nigeria (AVRS) which comprises of copyright owners of cinematograph films. The MCSN, which also comprises of copyright owners of musical works and sound recordings, has been in existence since 1984. However, it operated since 2010 without approval of the NCC. It only received the requisite approval from the NCC to operate as a collecting society in 2017. The approval was issued in compliance with the fiat of the Attorney-General of the Federation.⁸¹ As stated above, COSON's licence to operate as a collecting society is currently suspended.

At first glance, the approval of and continued existence of the accredited

⁷⁷ See s 63(1) of CAMA.

⁷⁸ See s 63(3) of CAMA.

⁷⁹ Marens and Wicks (n49) 275-277.

⁸⁰ Regulation 2(3).

⁸¹ See Daily Times 'Breaking: FG licenses MCSN as collecting society' (7 April 2017), available at <https://dailytimes.ng/news/breaking-fg-licenses-mcsn-collecting-society/> (accessed on 9 December 2017).

collecting societies may be accepted as evidence that the NCC's powers to issue or withhold approval are effective in facilitating appropriate corporate governance structures.⁸² It is however submitted that such evidence is rebuttable and therefore, not conclusive as there may be unknown corporate governance issues lurking in the corner.⁸³ In the case of SARAAL, it was not until the members took action in court for its liquidation that the corporate governance issues were known.⁸⁴ Significantly, the Copyright Review Commission in South Africa noted in its 2011 report that the regulatory authority should not have accredited SARRAL given that the latter's audited statement were consistently filed out of time suggesting that such was an indication that SARRAL would be unlikely to adhere to principles of good corporate governance.⁸⁵

The same argument applies to the powers of the NCC to renew a collecting society's licence where it expires or revoke the licence of a collecting society that no longer meets the conditions for the grant of licence.⁸⁶ This is because the assessment of compliance with recommended corporate governance structures and principles necessitates a consideration of "actual practices" of the company in question.⁸⁷ In the absence of periodic review of actual company practices, it may be difficult to ascertain whether the renewal or non-revocation of the licence of a collecting society has achieved the objective of facilitating appropriate corporate governance of collecting societies.⁸⁸

Under Regulation 8(2) of the CMO Regulations, each collecting society is required to prepare and submit a general report of its activities and an annual audited financial report in respect of its operations for the preceding year to the NCC not later than 1 July of each year. The audited financial report must show the total revenue, total sum and general nature of expenses, and payment of royalties to members in accordance with the collecting society's distribution policy. Where the collecting society fails to submit its audited accounts or where the NCC considers it necessary, it may order an

⁸² See s 168(1) of the Evidence Act as amended, Cap E14 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004, "When any judicial or official act is shown to have been done in a manner substantially regular, it is presumed that formal requisites for its validity were complied with".

⁸³ *Nigerian Air Force v. James* (2002) 18 NWLR (Pt.798) 295.

⁸⁴ See *Farlam* (n9) 19.

⁸⁵ *Ibid* at 44.

⁸⁶ Regulation 3(1)(iv) of the CMO Regulations.

⁸⁷ See OECD (n28) 11.

⁸⁸ See para 5 of the (Australian) Code of Conduct for Collecting Societies *supra*.

independent audit of the accounts and affairs of any collecting society.⁸⁹ The cost of such audit is to be borne by the relevant collecting society. By virtue of the CMO Regulations, the directors of any collecting society must act ethically and must keep the accounts and operations of the society devoid of fraud and unethical conduct.⁹⁰ Towards ensuring compliance, the NCC may also order an audit of the affairs and accounts of any collecting society. The NCC may, if it appears to it from the result of such audit that an offence has been committed by any of the officers of the collecting society, initiate criminal proceedings against the collecting society or its officers identified with the commission of the offence.⁹¹ Also, where a director has been indicted for an offence in relation to the result of an audit of the account of the collecting society, the CMO Regulations require that the collecting society suspend such director.⁹²

It is submitted that the consequences of non-compliance with the requirement to act ethically and ensure absence of fraud (or any crime) in the operation of the affairs of the collecting society, may be quite dissuasive. The threat of criminal prosecution and possible conviction may deter fraud in the management of the affairs of the collecting society.⁹³ Conversely, the requirement of payment of a fine of N50,000⁹⁴ (\$130) for non-compliance with directives to provide relevant information to members and/or users may be too low as to be appropriately dissuasive.

Collecting societies are permitted by the CMO Regulations to apply a percentage of their royalty collections not exceeding 30%, towards the expenses involved in discharging the functions of the collecting society.⁹⁵ Section 39(2)(a) requires an “aspiring” collecting society to be incorporated as a company limited by guarantee. A company limited by guarantee under s 26 of the CAMA is one formed for “promoting commerce, art, science, religion, sports, culture, education, research, charity or other similar objects”. It is therefore argued that to the extent that a collecting society is first incorporated as a company limited by guarantee under s 26 of the CAMA prior to an

⁸⁹ Regulation 10(2) of the CMO Regulations.

⁹⁰ Regulation 10(2).

⁹¹ Regulation 10(3).

⁹² Regulation 10(4).

⁹³ CA Wray and RK Hur ‘Corporate criminal prosecution in a post-Enron world: The Thompson memo in theory and practice’ (2006) 43 *Am Crim L Rev* 1095.

⁹⁴ Regulation 8(6).

⁹⁵ Regulation 11(1) of the CMO Regulations.

application to the NCC for a licence to operate as a collecting society, s 39(2)(b) of the Copyright Act does not aim to restrict a collecting society from exercising other functions aligned with the object of a company limited by guarantee. As such, while a collecting society must have the negotiation and grant of licences and/or collection and distribution of royalties as its functions, it is not limited to those functions only.⁹⁶ Such functions may therefore, include causes that promote culture and creativity. For instance, COSON's articles of association establish a trust, COSON Music Foundation constituted by the Governing Board for the welfare of members. The rules of the Foundation, the Board of Trustees of the Foundation and the Executive Secretary to the Board are all established and appointed by the Governing Board.⁹⁷ This is similar to the case in Europe for instance, where many national collecting societies set aside a percentage of revenues collected and use such for health insurance and pension funds of authors or the promotion of music and musical talents through prizes and awards.⁹⁸

Under the CMO Regulations, such deductions would be allowed within the limits set by the Governing Board of the collecting societies but must not exceed the stipulated percentage (30%) without the prior approval from the NCC.⁹⁹ Where this provision is breached, the NCC may issue a written caution to the officers of the collecting society and direct them to rectify such breach.¹⁰⁰ The power to caution erring officers apply in cases where the officers fail to provide information as per regulation 8(5); where the collecting society fails to send report of meetings as per regulation 9; and where the collecting society exceeds its authorized expenditure limit as per Regulation 11(3). Where the collecting society is cautioned for exceeding the approved 30% retention limit, it is not known the form, in which the required rectification may be made. For instance, will the directors be required to repay the sums spent in excess of the statutorily authorised limit? What are the consequences for the collecting society if the directors do not repay the funds spent? It is submitted that these questions are at the root of

⁹⁶ M Ficsor *Collective management of copyright and related rights* (2002) 149 to 153.

⁹⁷ See paragraph 70a of the Articles of association of COSON.

⁹⁸ See R Towse and C Handke 'Regulating copyright collecting societies: Current policy in Europe' (Paper presented at the Society for Economic Research on Copyright Issues (SERCI) Annual Congress Berlin 2007) 9. See I.A Olubiyi and K.I Adam 'An examination of the adequacy of the regulation of collecting societies in Nigeria' (2017) 5 *IPLJ* 93.

⁹⁹ Regulation 11(1).

¹⁰⁰ See Regulation 20(1).

deciphering the extent to which the power to caution erring officers facilitate good corporate governance of collecting societies in Nigeria.

The NCC may also caution the officers of a collecting society where they fail to provide users with information regarding repertoire and tariff-setting;¹⁰¹ where they fail to distribute royalties;¹⁰² where they fail to compensate users for unused licence occasioned by the negligence or fault of the collecting societies;¹⁰³ and in cases of unethical conduct.¹⁰⁴ Where a collecting society fails to carry out any action within the time stipulated, it may be directed to do so by the NCC, the NCC may suspend the licence of the collecting society for a period of time pending its compliance.¹⁰⁵ Further, where the collecting society has persisted in the conduct that led to the licence suspension in the first place, the NCC may revoke the licence of such collecting society.¹⁰⁶ Directors of collecting societies who have been cautioned twice without compliance on their part may be disqualified from holding directorship in any collecting society.¹⁰⁷ The next paragraphs consider whether these consequences for non-compliance are dissuasive and compelling.

In 2017, at a meeting of the Board of Directors of COSON, COSON's founding Chairman was removed and another Director (new Chairman) appointed in his stead pursuant to the powers of the Governing Board to elect a chairman from amongst its members under COSON's articles of association.¹⁰⁸ Subsequently, a General Meeting involving COSON's members (General Assembly) was held and the members who attended the meeting reinstated the ousted Chairman and appointed other members as directors. COSON also instituted an action in court in which an injunction was sought to restrain the new Chairman from parading himself as COSON Chairman.¹⁰⁹ Part of the complaint in the petition was that contrary to the articles of association, the matter of reinstating the ousted chairman was not on the agenda and yet was taken during the

¹⁰¹ Regulation 14.

¹⁰² Regulation 16.

¹⁰³ See Regulation 17.

¹⁰⁴ See Regulation 18.

¹⁰⁵ Regulation 20(2).

¹⁰⁶ *Supra*.

¹⁰⁷ Regulation 20(3).

¹⁰⁸ See Ezekude (n63).

¹⁰⁹ *Ibid*.

meeting. As a result, the NCC issued a directive to COSON instructing it not to give effect to the resolutions taken at the previous COSON's meeting (i.e. the resolution reinstating the ousted Chairman contrary to its articles of association) except the resolution on distribution of royalties to members. When COSON's reinstated Chairman and board refused to comply with NCC's directive, the NCC suspended COSON's licence.¹¹⁰

It is submitted that the exercise of the powers to suspend the operating licence of collecting societies under the CMO Regulations may be not be effective in facilitating adherence to good corporate governance. As a sanction for bad corporate governance, suspending the licence of a collecting society may not be appropriately dissuasive. It is pertinent to note the suspension of a collecting society's licence does not invalidate its membership of CISAC with its attendant advantages. Nor does such suspension or revocation invalidate the exclusive licence or assignment of performing rights assigned to the collecting society by its members.¹¹¹ Where CISAC membership and exclusive assignment remain valid, suspension may not offer the intended panacea to the incidences of bad corporate governance. It is suggested that the scenario might be different if CISAC rules required evidence of good standing with regulatory authority. Such requirement may at the risk of loss of membership, dissuade non-compliance with acceptable corporate governance standards and encourage compliance with regulatory directives.¹¹² Given the benefits of reciprocal agreements and CISAC membership, a loss of the reciprocal agreement enabled by CISAC membership may be dissuasive enough to compel compliance with the requirements of good corporate governance in any collecting society.

It is submitted that a similar argument may extend to the powers of the NCC to revoke the licence of a collecting society that fails to comply with directives despite the suspension of its licence. The NCC may also revoke the licence of a collecting society on its own or on application of an interested person,¹¹³ where such collecting society is in

¹¹⁰ See I Egbunike 'NCC Suspends Operating License of Copyright Society of Nigeria (COSON)', available at <http://www.copyright.gov.ng/index.php/news-events/item/432-ncc-suspends-operating-license-of-copyright-society-of-nigeria-coson> (viewed 16 May 2018).

¹¹¹ Bortloff (n36) 67; F Rose (ed) *Parties* (2013) 215-217; *Black's Law Dictionary* 2 ed (1910).

¹¹² See CISAC Professional rules for music societies (n44).

¹¹³ See Regulation 3 of the CMO Regulations.

breach of the Copyright Act, the Regulations and/or an order made by the NCC; where the collecting society no longer represents a substantial number of copyright owners; and instances where the collecting society failed to disclose a fact that would have led to a refusal of its licence application. Power to revoke a licence may also be exercised in cases where it would be reasonably justifiable to refuse an application for licence in the first place.¹¹⁴ As stipulated by s 17 of the Copyright Act, a collecting society cannot institute an action for copyright infringement if it does not have the approval of the NCC to operate as a collecting society. In other words, in the absence of the requisite approval from the NCC, a collecting society lacks the locus standi to institute an action for copyright infringement. This issue of locus standi of an organisation that does not have the approval of the NCC to operate as a collecting society has been subject of litigation in the Nigerian courts¹¹⁵ and has been significantly discussed in the literature.¹¹⁶ Specifically, the controversy has centred on whether, as an assignee or exclusive licensee of copyright, a collecting society still lacks locus standi to sue for copyright infringement in the absence of the requisite approval from the NCC.¹¹⁷ The most recent decision on this matter is in the case of Adeokin Records and another v Musical Copyright Society of Nigeria¹¹⁸ (Adeokin) issued by the apex court (the Supreme Court of Nigeria). In that case, the Supreme Court while observing that s 17 of the Copyright Act was not in force at the time the suit was instituted at the court of first instance, held that the Respondent/Plaintiff, being an undisputed owner, assignee and exclusive licensee of the copyright had the locus standi to institute an action against the appellant for alleged infringement of copyright.¹¹⁹ The decision of the Supreme Court was informed inter alia by its finding that the issue of locus standi was raised prior to the commencement of trial and as such, its consideration was limited to the statement of claim.¹²⁰ However, the Supreme Court noted that “it is this exercise of resorting to extraneous matters in order to

¹¹⁴ Ibid.

¹¹⁵ See *Compact Disc Technologies Limited and others v MCSN* (2010) LPELR-CA/L/787/2008; *MCSN v Adeokin Records* (2007) 13 NWLR (Pt 1052) 616; *MCSN v Detail* (1996) FHCLR 473; *Visafone Comm Ltd v MCSN* (2013) 5 NWLR (Pt 1347) 250.

¹¹⁶ *Odion and Oriakhogba* (n11) 518.

¹¹⁷ Ibid.

¹¹⁸ Unreported suit no SC/336/2008.

¹¹⁹ See pages 28 and 29 of the judgment.

¹²⁰ See pages 22-26 of the judgment.

resolve the question whether the Respondent had disclosed its locus standi that resulted in the learned trial Judge holding that she had “no doubt that the Plaintiff is a Collecting Society” and that from Exhibits A and B” there is manifest intent on the part of the Plaintiff to operate as a Collecting Society”.¹²¹ It is submitted that the inference from this statement may be that upon examination of the certificate of incorporation (Exhibit A in Adeokin) and the deed of assignment provided by copyright owners to a collecting society (Exhibit B in Adeokin), it will become apparent that the relevant organisation operates the business of a collecting society. Such examination would be conducted at trial and the relevant organisation will lack the locus to institute an action for copyright infringement if has not procured the licence or approval of the NCC to operate as such.¹²² The significance of this inference is strengthened by the court’s observation that the preliminary objection, which formed the subject of the appeal, was not and could not have been predicated on s 17 of the Copyright Act as that section was not in force at the time the suit was instituted at the court of first instance.¹²³ By making such reference and in remitting the suit to the court of first instance for a rehearing/trial,¹²⁴ the court may have implied that an organisation, which is shown (at trial) to be operating the business of a collecting society without the licence or approval of the NCC, will lack the locus to institute an action for copyright infringement.¹²⁵ The issue of locus standi, like any jurisdictional issue, may be raised at any time in the proceedings before a court, including during trial.¹²⁶

Corollary to the foregoing, it is submitted the revocation of the licence of a collecting society may be effective as it has the effect of removing the locus of the collecting society to institute an action for copyright infringement. Whether the collecting society sued as owner, assignee or exclusive licensee does not conclusively

¹²¹ See pages 23-24 of the judgment.

¹²² See page 31 of the judgment.

¹²³ Ibid.

¹²⁴ See page 35 of the judgment.

¹²⁵ According to the court on page 31 of the judgment, “the objection culminating in the trial court’s decision the subject of this appeal had no benefit of clairvoyancing that *section 15A would be promulgated to take away the right of the Respondent to maintain this suit on the cause list*”. (Italics mine). See also, See Okorie CI ‘Nigerian Supreme Court issues guidance on locus standi of collecting societies’ (forthcoming) *Journal of Intellectual Property Law & Practice*; Compact Disc Technologies Limited and others v MCSN *supra*.

¹²⁶ See *Yar’adua v Yandoma & Others* (2015) 4 NWLR (Pt 1448) 123 at 161 paras D-F.

settle the question of locus standi.¹²⁷ As noted above, the issue of locus standi is a jurisdictional issue, which may be raised at any time. In Adeokin, the locus standi issue was raised prior to the commencement of trial and the Supreme Court held that the trial court erred by not limiting itself to the statement of claim only.¹²⁸ However, if the issue of locus standi is raised at the time of trial or at address stage, the court will consider the evidence, which may at that time include mention of the objects of the collecting society. Such evidence will show that the objects of the collecting society are consistent with the functions stated in section 39(2) of the Copyright Act. Where a collecting society cannot sue copyright users to enforce the mandate of copyright owners, it would be unable to operate the core business of collecting and distributing royalties. Even where such collecting society can sue users for breach of contract or licensing agreement outside the Copyright Act,¹²⁹ it faces the threat of prosecution by virtue of s 39(5) of the Copyright Act. Section 39(4) of the Copyright Act makes it unlawful to carry on business as a collecting society without the requisite licence from the NCC. In the case of revocation of licence, the operation of the collecting society under a previous valid licence may be sufficient evidence that such organisation is carrying on business as a collecting society without the requisite licence.

Another issue relates to the question of the powers of the NCC to disqualify any officer of a collecting society from holding any management position in any collecting society where such officer has been cautioned for twice.¹³⁰ Regulation 19(3) provides that such disqualification shall be made unless the officer in question satisfies the NCC on why he should not be disqualified or as to why the disqualification should be lifted. It is submitted that, to the extent that such disqualification does not affect the livelihood of the relevant officers as authors and copyright owners, or the ability of the relevant officers to collect their royalties as copyright owners and members of the collecting society or from holding other directorship positions in other companies, it may not achieve the objective of facilitating good corporate governance. This position is strengthened by a comparison

¹²⁷ See Okorie CI (n126); DO Oriakhogba ‘Copyright collective management organizations in Nigeria: the locus standi conundrum resolved?’ (2018) *Journal of Intellectual Property Law & Practice*. Advance online publication. doi:10.1093/jiplp/jpy137

¹²⁸ See page 25 of the judgment.

¹²⁹ As suggested in MCSN v Adeokin unreported (n118). See also Odion and Oriakhogba (n11) 524.

¹³⁰ Regulation 20 (3).

with position of bank directors in Nigeria. By virtue of s 48(4) of the Banks and Other Financial Institutions Act,¹³¹ “any person whose appointment with a bank has been terminated or who has been dismissed for reasons of fraud, dishonesty or conviction for an offence involving dishonesty or fraud shall not be employed by any bank in Nigeria”. In the case of bank directors, however, such disqualification, if unchallenged or unsuccessfully challenged, spells the end of a banking career for such officers. Where such bank directors are shareholders, they would still be entitled to receive dividends as such shareholders. But as professionals,¹³² this may deprive the disqualified banker from a means of livelihood within the banking and financial sector. However, the same scenario may not play out in the case of directors of collecting societies. Directors of collecting societies are primarily creators and copyright owners and their disqualification as directors may not stop them from creating and owning copyright. Nor is their means of livelihood from their primary employment activity cut off, as is the case for disqualified bank directors. Given that directors of collecting societies are members and copyright owners in the first place, their disqualification in the event of being cautioned may lack the effect that may compel compliance.

Finally, where there is a dispute arising from any matter that falls within the purview of the CMO Regulations, the NCC has powers to set up a Dispute Resolution Panel to settle the dispute.¹³³ Accordingly, it is submitted that it is possible to refer a dispute regarding powers exercised at the meetings of a collecting society’s Governing Board and general assembly respectively to the NCC for resolution. This is because such dispute falls squarely within the purview of the CMO Regulations. The Copyright (Dispute Resolution Panel) Rules 2007 sets out the procedure involved in initiating proceedings before the Panel. The Rules do not describe the class of persons who may initiate proceedings. Essentially, the Panel acts as an arbitral body and is required to comply with the relevant provisions of the Arbitration and Conciliation Act 2004.¹³⁴ The Courts in Nigeria are often inclined to uphold the provisions of a valid arbitration agreement or provisions. The Supreme Court has also issued an order to stay court

¹³¹ Cap B3, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004.

¹³² A Sharma ‘Professional as agent: Knowledge asymmetry in agency exchange’ (1997) 22(3) *Academy of Management Review* 758.

¹³³ Regulation 15.

¹³⁴ See Copyright (Dispute Resolution Panel) Rules 2007.

proceedings where there is an arbitration agreement¹³⁵ and has in some cases, held that it was an abuse of the Court process for the respondent to institute a fresh suit in Nigeria against the appellant for the same dispute during the pendency of the arbitration proceedings in London.¹³⁶ While it is beyond the scope of this article to discuss the issue of whether the provisions of Regulation 15 of the CMO Regulations conflict with the right of any person to refer disputes to court, it is sufficient to note for the present purposes that members of a collecting society or members of the Governing Board of a collecting society may bring their disputes before the Panel.

It is submitted that the question of whether the powers of the NCC to resolve disputes is effective in facilitating good corporate governance depends on whether the NCC can compel participation of all relevant parties in the dispute resolution process. In this regard, it is noted that the provisions of the Australian Code of Conduct for Collecting Societies, which is binding on all signatory collecting societies, require such signatories to establish dispute resolution procedures that would be binding on them.¹³⁷ The availability of such opportunity may facilitate a review of the performance of collecting societies in applying principles of good corporate governance.

The analysis shows that the powers of the NCC in regulating the corporate governance of collecting societies under the CMO Regulations may not be sufficiently effective because in practical terms, they lack the force to compel compliance or dissuade non-compliance. Essentially, while the CMO Regulations allow the NCC to wield considerable powers in the corporate governance of collecting societies, the NCC may be unable to enforce good corporate governance due to the practical challenges highlighted above and as a result of enforcement gaps in the CMO Regulations.

5. How can the effectiveness of the NCC be improved?

The conclusions reached in the previous section leads to the question of how the effectiveness of the NCC in facilitating good corporate governance practices can be improved. Without dissuasive sanctions for non-compliance and/or appropriate resources for enforcing compliance, the exercise of power to facilitate good corporate governance may not be effective.

¹³⁵ Niger Progress Ltd. v. N.E.I. Corp. (1989) 3 NWLR (Part 107) 68.

¹³⁶ M.V. Lupex V. N.O.C (2003) 15 NWLR (Part 844) 469.

¹³⁷ See para 3.

One possible explanation for the ineffectiveness of the NCC's powers to facilitate corporate governance is the absence of provisions for the support of other institutions to compel or enforce compliance. Particularly, where there is appropriate institutional capacity and/or support that might contribute to effective enforcement, the effectiveness of the exercise of regulatory powers may be significantly improved. Where directives are issued requiring a collecting society to refrain from further expenditure pending the completion of some investigations, compliance may be effectively enforced if the NCC is able to procure a freeze on the relevant collecting society's bank accounts. In Nigeria, anti-corruption agencies such as the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC)¹³⁸ and Independent Corrupt Practices and other Related Offences Commission (ICPC)¹³⁹ respectively have powers to instruct¹⁴⁰ banks to put a freeze on relevant bank account pending the outcome of investigations.¹⁴⁰ Statutory provisions for collaboration with these bodies would enhance the effectiveness of the NCC in enforcing good corporate governance in collecting societies. Alternatively, the NCC may, with the support of copyright inspectors appointed under s 38 of the Copyright Act, solicit the support of those agencies to enable the appropriate enforcement of good corporate governance of collecting societies.

Apart from account freezes, it may be necessary to stipulate a fixed tenure for officers of collecting societies. Regulations prescribing a fixed tenure for officers of collecting societies may work proactively to ensure that the management of collecting societies stay in office long enough to implement good strategies and short enough to avoid conflicts of interests. The banking sector regulator, the Central Bank of Nigeria, successfully adopted such approach in the banking sector in order to address corporate governance issues in the banking sector.¹⁴¹ On the basis of handling finances for others,

¹³⁸ See Section 26 of the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (Establishment) Act, Cap E1, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004. Also, E Chianu 'Bankers' Books Evidence Act: Its Abuse by the Nigerian Police' (2002) 75 *The Police Journal* 111.

¹³⁹ See Section 45(1) of the Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Act Cap C31, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004. Also, Onuigbo and OI Eme 'Analyses of Legal Frameworks for Fighting Corruption in Nigeria: Problems and Challenges' (2015) 5(3) *Kuwait Chapter of the Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review* 1.

¹⁴⁰ See ss 28 and 29 of the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (Establishment) Act.

¹⁴¹ See Central Bank of Nigeria, 'Brief on Guidelines for tenure of managing directors of deposit money banks and related matters', available at https://www.cbn.gov.ng/out/2010/publications/pressrelease/gov/tenure_guideline19012010.pdf (viewed 20

collecting societies share similarities with banks, which owe a fiduciary duty of care, loyalty, honesty, and good faith to act in the best interests of its clients or stakeholders. Accordingly, fixing tenure for officers of collecting societies may likely achieve similar results as has been observed in the banking sector.

Further, it is also suggested that in considering the documents submitted for application for approval to operate and in considering applications for renewal of such approval, the NCC should pay greater attention to the membership agreement used by the relevant collecting society. It may be helpful to require that such membership agreement stipulate that the assignment given to the collecting society will become revocable in the event that such collecting society loses the approval of the NCC. Such requirement may help to ensure that offending collecting societies will lose their right to act for copyright owners where it fails to adhere to principles of good corporate governance.

As earlier noted, the challenge of ensuring that collecting societies adhere to the requirements of good corporate governance is not peculiar to Nigeria. However, many jurisdictions such as Australia, the UK have a code of conduct or code of corporate governance, which applies to or has been applied to collecting societies. In Australia, the Code of Conduct for Collecting Societies is mandatory on signatory collecting societies. Notably, compliance with the provisions and principles of the code is reviewed annually. It is submitted that such provisions offer a persuasive supplement to voluntary codes of conduct, which may not sufficiently address problems of bad corporate governance given the absence of statutory coercive force.¹⁴² Requiring collecting societies to demonstrate how they have complied with the code of corporate governance or code of conduct is likely to stimulate a positive corporate governance climate.¹⁴³ Furthermore, as observed in the previous section, provisions for civil actions and criminal prosecution against erring collecting societies for violation of statutory standards can help promote greater effectiveness in regulating the corporate governance of collecting societies in Nigeria.

June 2018); T Aburime, GL Gannon and CJ Corrado 'How Long Should Bank CEOs Continue?' (2011) *SSRN 1*. Available at: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=1970184> (viewed on 11 July 2018).

¹⁴² See W Gunathilake and PM Chandrakumara 'Why do corporations accept voluntary codes on corporate governance and why is the acceptance so rapid among the corporations? A theoretical explanation' (2010) *British Academy of Management 1*.

¹⁴³ VO Nmehielle and ES Nwauche 'External-Internal Standards in Corporate Governance in Nigeria' (2004) *GWU Law School Public Law Research Paper No. 115* The George Washington University Law School. Washington D.C.

6. Conclusion

The central message of this article is that the use of regulations to facilitate good corporate governance in collecting societies will not be effective if the regulatory authority is unable to compel compliance or dissuade non-compliance. Compliance may be compelled through the availability of dissuasive sanctions or through the availability of enforcement measures. To summarize the main findings, the powers of the regulatory authority have been somewhat effective in facilitating the establishment of good corporate governance structures (as opposed to good corporate governance practices) and may be effective with respect to criminal prosecution. Through the refusal of applications for collecting society licence, the NCC can ensure that aspiring and/or existing collecting societies establish structures that can make for good corporate governance practices. However, even with this outcome, the powers of the regulatory authority may not be significantly effective where collecting societies can refuse to comply with its directives without dissuasive sanctions.

Finally, suggestions and recommendation have been made to strengthen the NCC's effectiveness in facilitating good corporate governance in collecting societies. In essence, solutions such as account freezes, court orders which may be enforced through the court bailiffs and use of anti-corruption agencies may compel compliance with good corporate governance principles. At the end of the day, unless there are dissuasive sanctions for non-compliance, the exercise of regulatory powers to facilitate good corporate governance in collecting societies will not be effective in addressing that need. In the absence of good corporate governance, collecting societies may not survive. Similar considerations and the threat of corporate death have informed the establishment of code of conduct applied in many jurisdictions cited in previous sections of this paper. Such considerations should also inform the regulation of the corporate governance of collecting societies not only in Nigeria, but also all over Africa and the rest of the world.